

Measuring instrument 'Exchange of Information'

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The Government of the Netherlands has set targets for oral language proficiency which should be achieved by students at the end of elementary school [1]. Exchange of information is one of the tasks described in the conversations component of oral language skills [2]. The target level in this task is described as follows: 'The learner can give and ask for information and listen critically to this information in conversations inside and outside of school. The student can evaluate information and give a response [2].' The instrument described below can be used to measure the exchange of information. This instrument was developed to measure the effectiveness of the VR barrier game 'The exposition'[3].

Communication variables

To score the participants' utterances an audio recording is to be used. Scoring is done by counting how often three variables occur:

- Frequency of questions (the number of task-related questions the participant asks);
- Frequency of information sharing - response (how often the participant responds to the co-player);
- Frequency of information sharing - spontaneous (how often the participant spontaneously provides information).

These variables were created based on the research of Zhang et al. [4]. Zhang et al. created and tested nine different communication variables to evaluate the collaborative virtual environment they designed. From these nine communication variables, only the three variables that are functions of Exchange of Information according to Van der Beek et al. [2] are scored in this instrument. For each communication variable, the outcome measure is the number of times it occurred divided by the number of pure game minutes. The number of pure game minutes represents total game time minus in-game instruction time. Frequency scores per communication variables in utterances per minute are then calculated as follows: number of utterances / pure playing time in seconds x 60.

	Total	Per minute
Frequency of questions		
Frequency of information sharing - response		
Frequency of information sharing - spontaneous		

Some directions for scoring utterances

- An utterance consists of one or more words that form an isolated entity. An utterance can consist of up to 3 sentences [5].
- The type of utterance of each utterance is determined. If the participant asks a question, or shares information about the game (about what is seen or how to do something), then the researcher counts this utterance in the corresponding box. "Information sharing -

response" is a response to a question, hence this can be a complete sentence but can be only "yes" or "no" as well.

- Utterances that do not contain a task-related question or information are not counted. This includes, for example, expressions such as positive or negative feedback ("well done," "that was stupid"); exclamations or complaints ("yes," "stupid thing"); countdowns ("three, two, one, start"); information sharing that is not related to the task ("what class are you in?"); comments that are clearly not directed at the co-player (a participant wondering aloud where a picture is hanging while looking for it; reading the instruction aloud).

Inter-rater reliability

To get an overview of the inter-rater reliability of this measurement instrument, two recordings (311 utterances) were scored by both the researcher and a colleague. Where the distribution in utterances differed from each other, the smallest unit was used for numbering the utterances. If an utterance was considered one utterance by assessor 1, and two utterances by assessor 2, the "extra" utterance was scored as "other" by assessor 1. Using SPSS, Cohen's κ was calculated. A Cohen's κ starting at .61 counts as substantial (Landis & Koch, 1977). There was substantial agreement between the two assessors, $\kappa = .69$, $p < .001$ at 311 utterances.

References

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